

Predicting HCN, HCO⁺, multi-transition CO, and dust emission of star-forming galaxies

Extension to luminous infrared galaxies and the role of cosmic ray ionization

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Received / Accepted

ABSTRACT

The specific star-formation rate of star-forming ‘main sequence’ galaxies significantly decreased since $z \sim 1.5$, due to the decreasing molecular gas fraction and star formation efficiency. The gas velocity dispersion decreased within the same redshift range, apparently correlated with the star formation efficiency (inverse of the molecular gas depletion time). However, the radio–infrared (IR) correlation has not changed significantly since $z \sim 1.5$. The theory of turbulent clumpy starforming gas disks together with the scaling relations of the interstellar medium describes the large and small-scale properties of galactic gas disks. Here we extend our previous work on infrared, multi-transition molecular line, and radio continuum emission of local and high- z starforming and starburst galaxies to local and $z \sim 0.5$ luminous infrared galaxies. The model reproduces the IR luminosities, CO, HCN, and HCO⁺ line luminosities, and the CO spectral line energy distributions of these galaxies. We derive CO(1-0) and HCN(1-0) conversion factors for all galaxy samples. The relation between the star formation rate per unit area and H₂ surface density cannot be fit simply for all redshifts. There is a tight correlation between the star formation efficiency and the product of the gas turbulent velocity dispersion and the angular velocity of the galaxies. Galaxies of lower stellar masses can in principle compensate their gas consumption via star formation by radial viscous gas accretion. The limiting stellar mass increases with redshift. Whereas the radio continuum emission is directly proportional to the density of cosmic ray (CR) electrons, the molecular line emission depends on the CR ionization rate via the gas chemistry. The normalization of the CR ionization rate found for the different galaxy samples is about a factor of three to five higher than the normalization for the Solar neighborhood. This means that the mean yield of low energy CR particles for a given star formation rate per unit area is about three to ten times higher in external galaxies than observed by Voyager I.

Key words. Galaxies: evolution; Galaxies: ISM; Galaxies: magnetic fields; Galaxies: star formation; Radio continuum: galaxies; Radio lines: galaxies

Appendix C: Model variables

Table C.1. Model Disk Parameters.

Parameter	Unit	Explanation
$G = 5 \times 10^{-15}$	$\text{pc}^3 \text{yr}^{-1} \text{M}_{\odot}^{-1}$	gravitation constant
Q		Toomre parameter
R	pc	galactocentric radius
H	pc	thickness of the gas disk
l_{cl}	pc	cloud size
v_{rot}	pc yr^{-1}	<i>rotation velocity</i>
$\Omega = v_{\text{rot}}/R$	yr^{-1}	<i>angular velocity</i>
Φ_{V}		volume-filling factor
ρ	$\text{M}_{\odot} \text{pc}^{-3}$	disk midplane gas density
$\rho_{\text{cl}} = \rho/\Phi_{\text{V}}$	$\text{M}_{\odot} \text{pc}^{-3}$	cloud density
$\dot{\rho}_{*}$	$\text{M}_{\odot} \text{pc}^{-3} \text{yr}^{-1}$	star-formation rate
Σ	$\text{M}_{\odot} \text{pc}^{-2}$	gas surface density
Σ_{*}	$\text{M}_{\odot} \text{pc}^{-2}$	<i>stellar surface density</i>
$\dot{\Sigma}_{*}$	$\text{M}_{\odot} \text{pc}^{-2} \text{yr}^{-1}$	<i>star-formation rate</i>
$\xi = 9.2 \times 10^{-8}$	$\text{pc}^2 \text{yr}^{-2}$	constant relating SN energy input to SF
\dot{M}	$\text{M}_{\odot} \text{yr}^{-1}$	disk mass accretion rate (radial, within the disk)
v_{turb}	pc yr^{-1}	gas turbulent velocity dispersion
v_{rad}	pc yr^{-1}	gas radial velocity
v_{disp}^{*}	pc yr^{-1}	<i>stellar vertical velocity dispersion</i>
ν	$\text{pc}^2 \text{yr}^{-1}$	viscosity
$f_{\text{mol}} = \Sigma_{\text{H}_2}/(\Sigma_{\text{HI}} + \Sigma_{\text{H}_2})$		molecular fraction
α	$\text{yr M}_{\odot} \text{pc}^{-3}$	constant of molecule formation timescale
l_{driv}	pc	turbulent driving length scale
$\delta = 5$		scaling between the driving length scale and the size of the largest self-gravitating structures
$SFE = \dot{\Sigma}_{*}/\Sigma$	yr^{-1}	star-formation efficiency
$t_{\text{ff,cl}}$	yr	cloud free fall timescale at size l
$t_{\text{turb,cl}}$	yr	cloud turbulent timescale at size l (turbulent crossing time)
ϵ_{ff}		star formation efficiency per free-fall time $\epsilon_{\text{ff}} = \dot{\Sigma}_{*}/\Sigma_{\text{H}_2} \times t_{\text{ff}}(l_{\text{driv}})$

boldface: free parameters; *italic:* parameters determined from observations.

Table C.2. CR Model Parameters.

Parameter	Unit	Explanation
c	cm s^{-1}	speed of light
$m_{\text{e/p}}$	g	electron/proton mass
E	eV	CR particle energy
T	eV	CR kinetic energy
$n(E)$	cm^{-3}	CR particle density
$n_{\text{e/p}}$	cm^{-3}	CR electron/proton particle density
n_{H}	cm^{-3}	hydrogen density
$J(E)$	eV cm s^{-1}	CR mean flux or spectrum
$\zeta_{\text{H,H}_2}$	s^{-1}	CR ionization rate of atomic/molecular hydrogen
ϕ_{s}		CR secondary fraction
$\sigma(E)$	CR ionization cross section	
ϵ_{CR}	eV cm^{-3}	CR kinetic energy density
ϵ_{B}	eV cm^{-3}	magnetic energy density
t_{diff}	yr	CR diffusion timescale
U	Habing radiation field G_0	interstellar radiation field
B	G	magnetic field strength
$\xi_{\text{p/e}}$		normalization of the CR proton and electron densities
k		normalization factor of the local ionization fraction

Table C.3. Radio Continuum Model Parameters.

Parameter	Unit	Explanation
h	erg s	Planck constant
ν	Hz	frequency
ν_L	Hz	Larmor frequency
q		power law index of the CR electron density distribution $n_e(E) \propto E^{-q}$
ϵ_ν	erg s ⁻¹ cm ⁻² Hz ⁻¹ sr ⁻¹	synchrotron emissivity
L_{nu}	erg s ⁻¹	synchrotron luminosity
t_{sync}	yr	synchrotron timescale
t_{brems}	yr	bremsstrahlung timescale
t_{IC}	yr	inverse Compton timescale
t_{ion}	yr	ionization-energy loss timescale
t_π	yr	proton lifetime to pion losses timescale
t_{wind}	yr	Galactic wind advection timescale
α_f		fine structure constant
τ		optical depth
T_e	K	thermal electron temperature

Appendix D: PHIBSS2 and DYNAMO galaxies

Table D.1. PHIBSS2 galaxies from Freundlich et al. (2019).

Galaxy Name	short name	RA	DEC	z	$\log(M_*)$ (M_\odot)	SFR ($M_\odot \text{yr}^{-1}$)	$R_{\text{eff}}^{\text{disk}}$ (kpc)	inc ($^\circ$)	v_{max} (km s^{-1})	$\log(L_{\text{CO}(2-1)})$ ($\text{K km s}^{-1} \text{pc}^2$)
zCOSMOS 822872	xa53	10:02:02.09	+02:09:37.40	0.7000	11.46	47.3	4.1	63	374	9.97
zCOSMOS 805007	xc53	10:00:58.20	+01:45:59.00	0.6227	10.92	47.1	2.1	58	336	9.00
zCOSMOS 822965	xd53	10:01:58.73	+02:15:34.20	0.7028	10.95	39.5	6.1	34	190	9.82
zCOSMOS 811360	xe53	10:01:00.74	+01:49:53.00	0.5297	10.36	25.5	3.4	33	149	9.67
zCOSMOS 834187	xf53	09:58:33.86	+02:19:50.90	0.5020	11.08	18.6	5.2	56	268	9.75
zCOSMOS 800405	xg53	10:02:16.78	+01:37:25.00	0.6223	11.20	21.0	2.7	34	401	9.70
zCOSMOS 837919	xh53	10:01:09.67	+02:30:00.70	0.7028	10.73	18.2	2.2	37	225	9.23
zCOSMOS 838956	xi53	10:00:24.70	+02:29:12.10	0.7026	11.46	20.3	4.4	40	480	9.38
zCOSMOS 824759	xl53	10:00:28.27	+02:16:00.50	0.7506	11.23	28.6	2.6	43	463	9.72
zCOSMOS 810344	xm53	10:01:53.57	+01:54:14.80	0.7007	11.64	23.9	2.7	67	538	9.73
zCOSMOS 839268	xn53	10:00:11.16	+02:35:41.60	0.6967	11.04	24.2	3.9	38	287	9.57
zCOSMOS 828590	xo53	10:02:51.41	+02:18:49.70	0.6077	11.40	11.7	3.4	77	475	9.52
zCOSMOS 838696	xq53	10:00:35.69	+02:31:15.60	0.6793	10.92	26.9	9.9	70	168	9.49
zCOSMOS 816955	xr53	10:01:41.85	+02:07:09.80	0.5165	11.28	14.5	9.5	44	248	9.26
zCOSMOS 823380	xt53	10:01:39.31	+02:17:25.80	0.7021	11.04	22.7	3.7	53	275	9.64
zCOSMOS 831385	xu53	10:00:40.37	+02:23:23.60	0.5172	10.28	28.0	3.8	61	139	9.46
zCOSMOS 850140	xv53	10:01:43.66	+02:48:09.40	0.6248	10.80	23.1	2.7	68	237	9.81
zCOSMOS 824627	xw53	10:00:35.52	+02:16:34.30	0.7503	10.40	13.7	2.7	29	157	9.11
zCOSMOS 831870	114co001	10:00:18.91	+02:18:10.10	0.5024	10.18	29.0	1.8	30	139	9.48
zCOSMOS 831386	114co004	10:00:40.29	+02:20:32.60	0.6885	10.45	8.8	2.2	61	175	9.15
zCOSMOS 838945	114co007	10:00:25.18	+02:29:53.90	0.5015	10.71	4.1	6.2	77	163	9.15
zCOSMOS 820898	114co008	09:58:09.07	+02:05:29.76	0.6081	10.94	13.9	3.7	56	229	9.61
zCOSMOS 826687	114co009	09:58:56.45	+02:08:06.72	0.6976	10.45	21.4	3.9	56	160	9.43
zCOSMOS 839183	114co011	10:00:14.30	+02:30:47.16	0.6985	10.41	29.3	4.8	46	160	9.65
zCOSMOS 838449	114co012	10:00:45.53	+02:33:39.60	0.7007	10.59	10.0	1.0	40	283	9.41
AEGIS 30084	xa54	14:19:17.33	+52:50:35.30	0.6590	11.11	51.7	4.0	32	292	9.81
AEGIS 24556	xd54	14:19:46.35	+52:54:37.20	0.7541	10.36	28.9	2.7	33	155	9.58
AEGIS 25608	xe54	14:19:35.27	+52:52:49.90	0.5090	10.40	11.0	5.9	73	153	9.34
AEGIS 32878	xf54	14:19:41.70	+52:55:41.30	0.7683	10.71	19.9	4.3	44	200	9.51
AEGIS 3654	xg54	14:20:13.43	+52:54:05.90	0.6593	11.15	14.4	7.2	54	265	9.70
AEGIS 30516	xh54new	14:19:45.42	+52:55:51.00	0.7560	10.28	13.1	3.5	38	144	8.92
AEGIS 23488	114eg006	14:18:45.52	+52:43:24.10	0.5010	10.48	7.4	5.6	53	161	9.08
AEGIS 21351	114eg008	14:19:39.46	+52:52:33.60	0.7315	10.94	79.5	5.1	50	247	9.92
AEGIS 31909	114eg009	14:20:04.88	+52:59:38.84	0.7359	10.04	9.9	1.7	40	138	9.49
AEGIS 4004	114eg010	14:20:22.80	+52:55:56.28	0.6702	10.74	9.3	1.7	32	273	9.11
AEGIS 6274	114eg011	14:20:26.20	+52:57:04.85	0.5705	10.73	25.7	6.2	55	195	9.57
AEGIS 6449	114eg012	14:19:52.95	+52:51:11.06	0.5447	11.04	9.1	7.0	65	228	9.08
AEGIS 9743	114eg014	14:20:33.58	+52:59:17.46	0.7099	10.93	5.9	1.8	22	280	8.97
AEGIS 26964	114eg015	14:20:45.61	+53:05:31.18	0.7369	10.97	13.4	2.0	36	345	9.00
AEGIS 34302	114eg016	14:18:28.90	+52:43:05.28	0.6445	10.60	6.6	2.3	38	190	9.15
GOODS-N 21285	xa55	12:36:59.92	+62:14:50.00	0.7610	10.45	44.7	3.3	56	163	9.46
GOODS-N 6666	xb55	12:36:08.13	+62:10:35.90	0.6790	10.65	23.1	1.7	29	262	9.34
GOODS-N 19725	xc55	12:36:09.76	+62:14:22.60	0.7800	10.66	29.1	2.3	47	219	9.76
GOODS-N 12097	xd55	12:36:21.04	+62:12:08.50	0.7790	10.49	21.6	2.0	55	204	9.51
GOODS-N 19815	xe55	12:36:11.26	+62:14:20.90	0.7720	10.52	14.8	4.3	78	172	9.32
GOODS-N 7906	xf55	12:35:55.43	+62:10:56.80	0.6382	10.04	11.1	5.5	80	118	9.08
GOODS-N 19257	xg55	12:37:02.93	+62:14:23.60	0.5110	10.58	8.5	2.8	59	183	9.36
GOODS-N 16987	xh55	12:37:13.87	+62:13:35.00	0.7784	10.20	13.0	4.0	40	136	9.30
GOODS-N 10134	xl55	12:37:10.56	+62:11:40.70	0.7880	10.51	22.2	4.1	49	171	9.58
GOODS-N 30883	114gn006	12:36:34.41	+62:17:50.50	0.6825	10.40	23.8	3.1	74	157	9.71
GOODS-N 939	114gn007	12:36:32.38	+62:07:34.10	0.5950	10.87	8.9	7.7	46	234	9.57
GOODS-N 11532	114gn008	12:36:07.83	+62:12:00.60	0.5035	10.28	5.5	4.6	30	140	9.18
GOODS-N 25413	114gn018	12:36:31.66	+62:16:04.10	0.7837	10.40	32.8	2.0	36	168	9.40
GOODS-N 8738	114gn021	12:36:03.26	+62:11:10.98	0.6380	10.71	76.9	0.7	47	311	9.84
GOODS-N 11460	114gn022	12:36:36.76	+62:11:56.09	0.5561	10.11	6.8	0.6	24	133	8.57
GOODS-N 36596	114gn025	12:37:13.99	+62:20:36.60	0.5320	10.65	3.5	0.4	60	262	8.89
GOODS-N 21683	114gn032	12:37:16.32	+62:15:12.30	0.5605	11.11	7.6	2.5	28	304	8.85
GOODS-N 1964	114gn033	12:36:53.81	+62:08:27.70	0.5609	10.04	6.7	4.8	38	116	8.90
GOODS-N 33895	114gn034	12:36:19.68	+62:19:08.10	0.5200	10.87	8.7	5.3	64	213	9.83

The table displays the original values from Freundlich et al. (2019) except for the effective radius of the stellar disk $R_{\text{eff}}^{\text{disk}}$ and the maximum rotation velocity v_{max} , which is based on the total stellar mass and the I-band surface brightness profile (Sect. 3). The SFRs are estimated following a combination of UV and IR luminosities. The stellar masses are derived from SED fitting. For our model calculations the stellar masses and star formation rates were multiplied by a factor of 1.5, the maximum rotation velocity by a factor of $\sqrt{1.5}$. The SIMBAD designations of AEGIS and GOODS-N objects are [SWM2014] AEGIS and [SWM2014] GOODS-N.

Table D.2. DYNAMO galaxies.

Galaxy Name	RA	DEC	z	log(M _*) (M _⊙)	SFR (M _⊙ yr ⁻¹)	l _* (kpc)	v _{flat} (km s ⁻¹)	L _{CO} (K km s ⁻¹ pc ²)
G10-1	10 21 42.47	+12 45 18.73	0.1437	10.44	15.7	1.2	117	9.89
D20-1	20 52 09.08	-00 30 39.32	0.0705	10.47	4.7	3.4	134	9.58
G04-1	04 12 19.71	-05 54 48.70	0.1298	10.81	21.3	2.8	260	10.41
G20-2	20 44 02.91	-06 46 57.91	0.1411	10.33	18.2	2.1	150	9.86
D13-5	13 30 07.03	+00 31 52.48	0.0754	10.73	17.5	2.0	180	10.11
G08-5	08 54 18.74	+06 46 20.57	0.1322	10.24	10.0	1.8	220	9.99
D15-3	15 34 35.40	-00 28 44.54	0.0671	10.73	8.3	2.2	240	10.11
G14-1	14 54 28.31	+00 44 34.49	0.1323	10.35	6.9	1.1	150	9.84
C13-1	13 26 39.42	+01 30 01.35	0.0788	10.55	5.1	4.2	223	9.91
C22-2	22 39 49.34	-08 04 18.05	0.0712	10.34	3.2	3.4	200	9.50
SDSS 024921-0756	02 49 21.42	-07 56 58.67	0.1530	10.48	10.5	1.1	84	10.12
SDSS 212912-0734	21 29 12.14	-07 34 57.69	0.1840	10.85	53.0	1.3	105	10.26
SDSS 013527-1039	01 35 27.11	-10 39 38.55	0.1270	10.85	25.3	1.6	190	10.22
SDSS 033244+0056	03 32 44.77	+00 58 42.08	0.1820	10.86	60.5	1.9	239	10.16
IRAS08339+6517	08 38 23.09	+65 07 16.05	0.0191	10.04	12.1	1.0	150	9.32

SFRs were calculated from the emission-line flux using the extinction-corrected H α line luminosity. The stellar masses were derived from the 4000-Å break strength, the Balmer absorption-line index H δ_A (Kauffmann et al. 2003). The SIMBAD designation of the first 10 sources is [GGM2014].

Fig. D.1. Fig. 1 continued.

Fig. D.2. Fig. 1 continued.

Fig. D.3. Fig. 1 continued.

Fig. D.4. Fig. 1 continued.

Fig. D.5. Fig. 1 continued.

Fig. D.6. Fig. 1 continued.

Fig. D.7. Fig. 1 continued.

Fig. D.8. Fig. 1 continued.

Fig. D.9. Fig. 1 continued.

Fig. D.10. Fig. 1 continued.

Fig. D.11. Fig. 1 continued.

Fig. D.12. IR SEDs of $z \sim 0.5$ LIRGs. Fig. 5 continued.

Fig. D.13. IR SEDs of $z \sim 0.5$ LIRGs. Fig. 5 continued.

Fig. D.14. IR SEDs of local LIRGs. Fig. 5 continued.